

subjected biaxial bending fatigue, provided the permanent deflection of the plates has been employed as an additional fatigue failure criterion.

5. REFERENCES

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EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF FAILURE -CRITERIA APPLIED TO MULTI-DIRECTIONAL LAMINATES OF GLASS-FIBRE REINFORCED POLYESTER (GRP)

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ABSTRACT

Failure of multidirectional laminates composed of glass-fibre reinforced polyester has been studied by means of biaxial tests on flat cross-shaped specimen provided with a small circular hole in the centre.

During failure initiating, which often occurred at the edge of the hole, the stress distribution along the edge has been determined. This distribution has been subjected to the Tsai-Wu failure criterion, yielding a distribution of safety factors for each consisting layer.

The ultimate strength is approximately three times as high as would be expected from the first-ply failure criterion.

Composite materials, Biaxial testing, Fracture, GRP-laminates.

1. INTRODUCTION

Multi-directional laminates can be considered as composed of identical orthotropic lamina. For the orthotropic lamina, a failure criterium described by equation (1) has been adopted by several authors.

$$F_i \sigma_i + F_{ij} \sigma_j = 1 \quad (1)$$

Under plane stress conditions in principal directions, equation (2) can be derived.

$$F_1 \sigma_1 + F_2 \sigma_2 + F_{11} \sigma_1^2 + F_{22} \sigma_2^2 + F_{66} \sigma_6^2 + 2F_{12} \sigma_1 \sigma_2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

F_i and F_{ii} ($i=1,2,6$) can be expressed in the unidirectional tension and compression strengths X and X' in fibre direction, Y and Y' perpendicular to the fibres, and the shear strength S .

F_{12} has to be derived from a biaxial test, for which we have chosen an in-plane test on a flat specimen.

In figure (1) a view has been given of the geometry of a cross-formed flat specimen. In the circular centre area (diameter 100mm) the laminate to investigate has been applied. Attempts to initiate failure within the inside area only succeeded by applying a hole in

the centre of the specimen (diameter 14mm). This phenomenon has lead us to an approach of subjecting the stress distribution around the hole to a failure criterion, in order to verify the validity of the criterion.

Two methods of determining the stress distribution around a circular hole in orthotropic plates will be discussed. The first method is based upon real variable expressions, yielding the exact solution for stress distributions in an infinite orthotropic plate. The second method is by means of a finite element analysis.

figure 1. View of biaxial specimen.

A biaxial state of stress has been implied as a result of external loading the specimen in two directions, coinciding with the specimen axes of symmetry. Load is applied by means of two servo-controlled hydraulic jacks attached to two independent reaction frames. In order to avoid rotation and introduction of external shear forces, it is necessary to choose a symmetrical laminate composition.

The strain has been measured in the two main directions by means of strain-gauges. Assuming a homogeneous stress and strain distribution within the centre area, the laminate stress can be calculated from known laminate properties in the two principal directions via inversion of equation (3).

$$\epsilon_i = S_{ij} \cdot \sigma_j \quad (3)$$

S_{ij} can be determined directly by uniaxially testing in principal material directions.

The multidirectional laminates are composed of 8 unidirectional layers of glass-fibre reinforced polyester of types listed below:

- A $(0^\circ, +45^\circ, -45^\circ, 0^\circ)_S$
- B $(+45^\circ, 0^\circ, -45^\circ, 0^\circ)_S$
- C $(+45^\circ, -45^\circ)_{2S}$
- D $(0^\circ)_8$
- F $(0^\circ, +90^\circ)_{2S}$
- K $(0^\circ, +25^\circ, -25^\circ, 0^\circ)_S$

All these types are orthotropic and symmetric; the lamina thickness is nominally 0.25mm, yielding a total laminate thickness of 2mm.

2. STRESS DISTRIBUTION AROUND A CIRCULAR HOLE IN ORTHOTROPIC PLATES.

The calculation of stress distributions in orthotropic plates normally is realized by

means of complex functions. The expressions derived for stress concentrations around holes are relatively simple, but still contain complex variables. In [2] these expressions are given, using real variables, applied on the situation of figure (2).

figure 2. Hole in an infinite orthotropic plate.

Elastic constants can be derived from the elastic properties of the orthotropic laminate, and are defined as follows:

$$r = \sqrt{E_{xx}/E_{yy}} \tag{4a}$$

$$a = E_{xx}/2G_{xy} - \nu_{xy} \tag{4b}$$

$$s = \sqrt{2(r+a)} \tag{4c}$$

In order to calculate the tangential stress distribution along the edge of the hole, a geometrical constant N is used, defined by equation (5); the stress distribution due to loading p_x and p_y can be calculated through equation (6a) and (6b) respectively:

$$N = \sin^4\vartheta + r^2\cos^4\vartheta + 2a\cos^2\vartheta.\sin^2\vartheta \tag{5}$$

$$\sigma_\vartheta/p_x = [(1+s)\sin^2\vartheta - r\cos^2\vartheta]/N \tag{6a}$$

$$\sigma_\vartheta/p_y = [r(r+s)\cos^2\vartheta - r\sin^2\vartheta]/N \tag{6b}$$

The final stress distribution due to a biaxial state of stress can be calculated by the superimposing of equations (6a) and (6b).

figure 3. Distribution of tangential stress.

The ultimate stress distribution for specimen A05, resulting from field stresses $\sigma_x=138.2$ and $\sigma_y=39.7$ N/mm², calculated via equation (3), has been depicted in figure (3) with reference "spies". In the same diagram, the result of a finite element analysis has been represented (reference "diana").

3. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS.

A linear static analysis has been performed by means of the DIANA Finite Element System.

A model assembled of 848 layered quadratic shell-elements (type CQ40L) has been used. This element type has the option of orthotropic layers in distinct directions. For reasons of symmetry, one quarter of the real model suffices.

The inner three rings consist of 90 8-layer elements each. The material properties of the layers have been specified according to unidirectional tests. Because E_{22} and G_{12} both are nonlinear, a mean value has been chosen for the linear elastic analysis.

The remaining elements have been composed of one layer, with material properties according to the general laminate properties.

Figure (4) gives a view of the mesh generation of the finite element model.

figure 4. Mesh generation of biaxial finite element model.

For ultimate loading combinations F_x and F_y the element stresses have been evaluated in local layer axes, coinciding with the fibre directions, according to a 2x2x3 Simpson integration over the layer thickness, in order to facilitate interpretation of strains and stresses.

The tangential stress distribution along the edge of the hole has been determined by transformation of $(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_6)$ to the tangential direction, and additioning the stresses of the 8 consisting layers. The result of this analysis has been represented in figure (3).

Both distributions are shaped identically, but the values of the FE-analysis are explicitly higher in all directions. This can be explained by the fact, that the hole is relatively large compared with the dimension of the circular inner part of the biaxial

specimen. The peak at $\vartheta=90^\circ$ could be caused by model imperfections, and will be investigated furthermore.

For specimen A05 and A09 the coarse of strain within the inner circular part for ultimate loading in X- and Y-direction have been evaluated, in order to check the reliability of the strain measurements. The results have been represented in figure (5).

figure 5. Coarse of strain in x- and y-direction.

For A05 in X-direction, and for A09 in Y-direction the agreement between calculated and measured strain values is very good. In both other directions however there is less agreement. It is possible that the disagreement could be explained with a nonlinear behaviour in Y-direction.

It is obvious, that a good estimation of stresses by means of strain-gauge measurements is very difficult in this special case of testing.

figure 6. Distribution of $1/S_f$

4. EVALUATION OF ULTIMATE STRESSES AND CONCLUSIONS.

From the stress distribution ($\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_6$) for each layer in all elements along the edge of the hole, a safety-factor S_f can be derived by substituting $S_f(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_6)$ into equation (2) and solving the linear quadratic equation in S_f .

Because F_{12} is yet unknown, a value $-0.5 \sqrt{F_{11} \cdot F_{22}}$ has been substituted, as suggested by Tsai-Hahn [2].

In figure (6) the distribution of $1/S_f$ has been represented for each individual lamina direction.

For test A05 a minimum S_f value 0.35 has been determined at $\vartheta=60^\circ$, thus the reciprocal value of S_f reaches a maximum of $\gamma=2.87$.

Close observation of the edge of the hole during increase of load showed no delamination at all, until failure initiation occurred. Nearly simultaneously the ultimate load was reached. Depending on the load ratio between X- and Y-direction, initiation of failure occurred in two or four symmetrical located points at the same time.

Despite of the fast development of failure after initiation, we succeeded sometimes in unloading before total failure of the specimen.

Specimen A05 and A09 both failed at $\vartheta=\pm 65^\circ$. This direction coincides with the area where first-ply failure was predicted. So there seems to be a relationship between the direction of initiation of failure, and the lowest safety-factor. However, in this particular case the ultimate laminate strength turned out to be nearly 3 times as high as predicted with the first-ply failure criterion.

Attempts to obtain a better prediction of strength by choosing other values of F_{12} did not succeed.

In order to draw general conclusions, the experimental results which are available at this moment have to be analysed thoroughly furthermore. A nonlinear analysis will be executed in order to study the influence of nonlinear material parameters.

Moreover it would be of interest to expand this research to other kinds of composite materials.

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